

Research Brief: Community Infrastructure to Further Open Research Software

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[Preliminary Investigation](#)

1. Summary

At Invest in Open Infrastructure (IOI), we are working to understand the landscape of research software and to identify the gaps, challenges, and opportunities for advancing its sustainability and resilience. This research brief is a first output of a broader project (funded by the Sloan Foundation, October 2024-January 2025) in which we are conducting desk research and interviews to inform a set of findings and recommendations regarding the health and future development opportunities for this rapidly growing ecosystem.

Research software as a primary output in its own right has gained attention in recent years, particularly as the focus on data, spurred in part by mandates like the OSTP Nelson memo, has also increased. We are witnessing a process of formalization and institutionalization of this open science-related field, with the development of best practices (e.g. FAIR Principles for Research Software), newly recognized roles (e.g.,

Research Software Engineer), thriving forums (e.g. US-RSE, Software Sustainability Institute, Journal of Open Source Software), and functions both in and beyond the academic community. With this process, there is growth in initiatives, organizations, and services — or “infrastructures” — working to support the development, maintenance, discovery, sharing, reviewing, and citation of research software, with the aim of furthering open, reproducible, and equitable research. Many of these infrastructures are community-governed and/or open to varying extents; this signals that the research community's constituents are involved in steering the growth and evolution of the research software field. Our research seeks to understand the degree to which existing research software infrastructure is open and what might help this ecosystem to thrive and sustainably develop. Though this infrastructure is the focus of this work, desk research for the project involved a look across the entire landscape of related issues and players.

This brief summarizes and provides a bibliography for our desk research; it also describes our overall approach in this project.

2. Research objectives

We want to understand what is happening to date in community infrastructure for research software across disciplines. Our guiding objectives are to identify:

- Existing connections between different research software infrastructure initiatives, and where new connections can be built to advance sustainability and resilience of the ecosystem
- Areas in the ecosystem where there is overcrowding/excessive functional overlap, and where there are gaps, blockers, vulnerabilities, and/or critical dependencies that need to be addressed
- Indications of what helps infrastructure services and initiatives succeed in adding value to the research software ecosystem

2.1 Qualitative approach

We follow a qualitative approach combining desk research and analysis, and community engagements. We are conducting interviews (about 15) with key stakeholders, identified in part from the desk research we conducted. Interviews will serve, in part, to validate, correct and/or round out information gathered from desk research.

3. Desk research

To inform the project direction and approach, IOI senior researcher Gail Steinhart prepared an extensive collection of desk research sources and notes, including identifying relevant:

- Organizations, services, and initiatives, categorized by type — for example, documentation and workflow tools, software publishers and repositories and communities of practice
- A core, annotated bibliography of more than 50 sources, to which additional sources and notes were added by project team members during October 2024 (Appendix B).

3.1 Desk research findings summary

Several themes, areas of agreement, and underserved needs surfaced through the desk research.

- There are broad agreements on and efforts toward the need to recognize and reward research software as a primary research output
- The research software community is converging on principles and best practices to ensure that the development of research software advances open, collaborative science
- The lack of common, formal recognition for this work has been a disincentive for busy researchers, who generally have had no/little formal software development training, to take the (often considerable) time necessary to prepare software for sharing and (re)use
- Funding and sustainability concerns are rampant and unresolved
- Popular, convenient options for sharing are not necessarily “open”
- Software citation is a challenge for researchers and publishers
- Research software includes a variety of concerns and needs that are distinct from but situated within the broader context of:
 - Software discovery and use (including the extent to which software may or may not be designed for reuse, and software metadata standards and management)
 - Software preservation
 - Data generated or analyzed by software
 - Differentiating between code (e.g. for statistical analyses), vs. full-fledged software and other stages of research software work
 - Maintenance and open-source software management
 - Research reproducibility
 - Concerns about equity, diversity, inclusion, and accessibility
 - Community building and engagement

Identifying connections in the overall landscape at a high level is one of the objectives of this project. Key categories include:

1. Tools/services
2. Actors (individuals, organizations/initiatives, networks)

3. Policies and practices
4. Objects, e.g. source code, containers, metadata, etc.

Building on previous landscape studies and categorizations¹, we have compiled a list of key research software tools/services, actors, and policies and practices as a starting point for the interviews and further desk research (see Appendix A).

4. Interview Instrument and Questions

We developed a [semi-structured interview guide](#) informed by the desk research to facilitate the interviews with approximately (as of this writing) 15 participants. Our research protocol and question bank will be made available at the conclusion of these interviews. It includes five main sections. Depending on the role and involvement of participants in the ecosystem:

- We ask about the role and involvement in organizations and communities that focus on research software as an output of research in its own right
- If applicable, we ask about the objectives of the organizations participants represent, strengths, challenges, threats, and risks they face, particularly how the organization or initiative is funded and otherwise supported
- Beyond individual organizations and initiatives, we ask participants' opinions on the challenges and risks facing the sector in areas they are familiar with
- We ask for participants' views on gaps and redundancies in the broader ecosystem and the relative merits of multiple, overlapping efforts toward shared goals vs. sharing services and resources
- We ask for recommendations on additional stakeholders to speak with and additional questions and areas to explore

5. Acknowledgments

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Additional information about how the work of IOI is funded can be found here:

<https://investinopen.org/about/how-were-funded/>

¹ Examples of previous landscape studies and categorizations in the space referenced include Katz et al. (2020), Martinez (2022), and Maphanga & Van der Walt (2023).

6. Appendix A: Key research software tools/services, actors, and policies and practices

Name and URL	Primary key category ²
Astrophysics Source Code Library (ASCL)	Tool/service
Astropy	Tool/service
Better Scientific Software	Actor
Bioconductor	Tool/service
bio.tools	Tool/service
Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC)	Actor
The Carpentries	Tool/service
CodeMeta	Tool/service
Code Refinery	Tool/service
Common Workflow Language	Tool/service
CoMSES Network (Network for Computational Modeling in the Social and Ecological Sciences)	Actor
Consortium for the Advancement of Scientific Software (CASS)	Actor
CZI Essential Open Source Software for Science	Actor
Dutch national guide to research software management	Policies and practices
Emulation as a service infrastructure (EaaS)	Policies and practices?
ELIXIR	Actor
EVERSE (European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence)	Actor
FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS)	Policies and practices
FORCE11 (selected working groups)	Actor
Galaxy	Tool/services
Helmholtz Digital Services for Science	Tool/service

² There are 4 key categories: 1) Actors (individuals, organizations/initiatives, networks), 2) Policies and practices 3) Objects (e.g. source code, containers, metadata), 4) Tools/services; while an organization/initiative/service can belong in multiple key categories, in this table, we identify the “primary key category” for each, which is the most relevant category in the context of this research.

Name and URL	Primary key category ²
Interoperable Design of Extreme-scale Application Software (IDEAS)	Policies and practices?
JBrowse	Tool/service
Journal of Open Research Software	Tool/service
Journal of Open Source Software	Tool/service
Project Jupyter	Tool/service
Machine Learning in R (MLR)	Tool/service
Matplotlib	Tool/service
NASA (through relevant funding initiatives such as TOPS F.15 High Priority Open-Source Science)	Actor
Netherlands eScience Center	Actor
Network Analysis Software Collective (NASCoI)	Actor
Nextflow	Tool/service
National Institutes of Health (NIH, US; through funding initiatives such as RSE Award)	Actor
Numfocus	Actor
Numpy	Tool/service
OntoSoft (EarthCube)	Tool/service
Open-Source Science (OSSci)	Actor
Pandas	Tool/service
PANGEO	Actor
PLOS Computational Biology: Software	Tool/service
Posit	Tool/service
Python Software Foundation	Actor
pyOpenSci	Tool/service
rOpenSci	Tool/service
ReproZip	Tool/service
Research Data Alliance (select working groups)	Actor
Research Object Crate (RO-Crate)	Tool/service
Research Software Alliance (ReSA)	Actor

Name and URL	Primary key category ²
Research Software Directory	Tool/service
RSE networks, e.g. UK RSE Society , RSSE Africa , and RSE Asia	Actors
SciCrunch	Tool/service
SingularityCE	Tool/service
Snakemake	Tool/service
Software Heritage	Tool/service
Software Preservation Network	Actor
Software Sustainability Institute	Actor
The Turing Way	Actor
US Research Software Sustainability Institute (URSSI)	Actor
Working towards Sustainable Software for Science: Practice and Experiences (WSSSPE)	Actor
Zenodo	Tool/service

7. Appendix B: Bibliography

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